

ISic1663

I.Sicily inscription 1663

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

decree (?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

area of the bouleuterion, S. Nicola

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale
Archeologico Pietro Griffo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR136229

1. ΣΕΙΝ [---]
2. ΜΕΝΑ [---]
3. ΔΩΣΕΙ [---]
4. ΟΣΑΚΙ [---]
5. ΑΠΟΓΡ [---]
6. ΠΡΟΝΟΟ [---]
7. ΑΓΑΘΑΠ [---]
8. ΝΑΤΟΥ Μ [---]
9. ΣΤΑΣΑΙ Ε [---]
10. ΑΓΩΝΑΤ [---]
11. ΠΑΣΙΦΑΝ [---]
12. ΤΑΙΧΑΡΙ [---]
13. ΤΟΔΕΔ [---]
14. ΑΝΑΘΕ [---]
15. ΑΥΥΩ Μ [---]
16. ΞΑ Ν [---]

contromarche e incisioni. *Epigraphica*. 76: 63-80. At 63-66

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